

The study of the influence of gypsum binders used for glass-metal connections in conservation works on the glass surface degradation

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Introduction

The problem of the degradation of historical objects is very complex. Changes of the environmental parameters in museums, such as **temperature** and **humidity**, cabinets made from the inappropriate **materials emitting organic compounds**, such as formic acid, acetic acid and formaldehyde, as well as the materials used in conservation work **have a significant impact on the museum collections**. This study has been carried out in order to determine parameters related to programming preventive maintenance for objects constituting a set of two different materials and exhibited in museums as a whole. The research served to exclude harmful properties of the proposed or used binder materials in conservation works.

Experimental

Sample: glass* + gypsum binder + piece of metal

Corrosion agent: 40% formaldehyde vapours

Time duration: 69 days

Temperature: 20,5°C

The corrosion simulation that takes place in the museum surroundings has been made on high alkaline glass, joined by gypsum binders based on old conservator recipes with two sorts of metal - copper and brass. The experiment were carried out in average temperature 20,5°C in closed desiccator. After 69 days, samples were taken out of the desiccator, and then examined both macroscopically and microscopically.

*Glass composition: 73,03% SiO₂; 16,34% K₂O; 8,8% CaO; 0,19% Na₂O; 0,75% B₂O₃; 0,59% MgO; 0,14% BaO; 0,064% PbO; 0,065% Al₂O₃

Optical Microscopy

Optical microscope images were taken by Nikon LV UDM 100 with a 5 MPx CCD camera. Pictures obtained using 10x magnification lens were analyzed by NIS Elements ver. 3.4 software.

Even with relatively short time of experiment we can see with the use of optical microscope significant changes on glass surface.

Characterization of corrosion products

Raman Spectroscopy

Raman spectra were recorded in the range of (200–1400) cm⁻¹ by RENISHAW inVia Reflex Raman spectrometer with a Leica DM2500 microscope. A 532 nm laser with 28.5 mW power was used as the excitation source for a spot of about 1 mm diameter.

Only locations with significant corrosion were analyzed.

According to the S.T. Japan database some probable corrosion products were identified.

The full list of identified corrosion products is given in the table (Characterization of the corrosion products).

Characterization of corrosion products				
	A	B	C	D
Raman shift/cm ⁻¹	590, 680, 690, 900	590, 680, 690, 900	440, 730, 880	590, 680, 690, 900
ST Japan Spectral databases	Chabazite (Zeolite group) Ca Al(2) Si(4) O(12) .6H(2)O	Cristobalite (Silica group) Si O(2)	Chabazite (Zeolite group) Ca Al(2) Si(4) O(12) .6H(2)O	Harmotome (Zeolite group) (Ba,K)1-2 (Si,Al)8 O(16) .6H(2)O
	Chabazite (GSJ M18886) Ca2Al2Si4O12 x 6H2O	Stilbite (Zeolite group) Na Ca(2) Al(5) Si(13) O(36) .14H(2)O	Pseudomalachite (Cu-hydroxyphosphate) Cu(5) [PO(4)]2 (OH)4 . H(2)O	Gmelinite (Zeolite group) [Na(2),Ca] Al(2) Si(4) O(12) .6H(2)O
	Pseudomalachite (Cu-hydroxyphosphate) Cu(5) [PO(4)]2 (OH)4 . H(2)O	Stellerite (Zeolite group) Ca Al(2) Si(7) O(18) . 7H(2)O	Yugarwaralite (GSJ M15325) CaAl2Si6O16.4H2O	Stilbite (Zeolite group) Na Ca(2) Al(5) Si(13) O(36) .14H(2)O
	Pyrophyllite (N/Si100) Al4(Si8O20)(OH)4	Gmelinite (Zeolite group) [Na(2),Ca] Al(2) Si(4) O(12) .6H(2)O	Libethenite (Cu-phosphate) Cu(2) [PO(4)] (OH)	Chabazite (GSJ M18886) Ca2Al2Si4O12 x 6H2O
	Epitode (GSJ M15952) Ca2Fe3+Al2(Si2O7)(SiO4)O(OH)	Chabazite (GSJ M18886) Ca2Al2Si4O12 x 6H2O	Sericite (GSJ M17954) K2O x 3Al2O3 x 6SiO2 x 2H2O	Pyrophyllite (N/Si100) Al4(Si8O20)(OH)4

SEM

Examination of glass surfaces was carried out using the Nova Nanosem 200 scanning electron microscope, FEI, and the EDEX EDS detector was used. Large amounts of carbon were detected on each sample, the glass in some places is covered with a gel layer, which proves the high concentration of silicon and oxygen on its surface. In addition, there is quite high concentration of potassium, which can be a sign of ion exchange processes.

Elemental composition of the glass surface for selected points

	points					
	A		B		C	
	1	2	1	2	1	2
El.	atom. [%]					
C	19,44	18,96	25,00	52,54	13,47	24,79
O	45,07	51,37	40,66	34,72	63,71	59,05
Na	11,25	14,12	1,34	1,44	0,57	0,79
Mg	0,37	0,25	0,27	0,36	0,56	0,44
Al	0,34	0,31	1,04	1,51	1,09	0,24
Si	5,47	4,14	19,74	5,22	3,91	3,94
S	12,85	7,84	0,14	1,23	8,52	4,12
K	0,67	0,70	7,32	1,14	0,59	0,72
Ca	4,54	2,24	4,13	1,21	7,58	5,91
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

Conclusions

Materials used for connections should have neutral character on the historical objects and should not cause any degradation of the connected elements. However, the performed tests confirmed that gypsum binders used for glass-metal connections have significant impact on the formation of permanent changes at the surface of the glass objects.